

Some Lanthanide-EDTA Ternary Complexes with Catechol, Resorcinol and Phloroglucinol

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The proton-ligand stability constants of catechol, resorcinol and phloroglucinol and the metal-ligand stability constants of the 1 : 1 binary complexes, ML ($M = \text{La}^{3+}$, Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} or Sm^{3+} and $L = \text{cat}$, res or phl) and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes, MAL ($M = \text{La}^{3+}$, Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} or Sm^{3+} ; $A = \text{edta}$; $L = \text{cat}$, res or phl) have been determined at 28° and $\mu = 0.2M$ (NaClO_4) using Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique. The stability constant values have been found to lie in the order $\log K_{MA}^M \gg \log K_{ML}^M > \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$. The ΔF and $\Delta \log K$ values have been calculated. The stability of the complexes ML as well as MAL is found to be in the sequence $\text{cat} > \text{res} > \text{phl}$ with respect to the secondary ligands, and $\text{La}^{3+} < \text{Ce}^{3+} < \text{Pr}^{3+} < \text{Nd}^{3+} < \text{Sm}^{3+}$ with respect to the metal ions.

Validity of Born's relation has been tested for the ternary complexes MAL. The $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values have been correlated with the standard entropies, standard electrode-potentials and ionic potentials of the lanthanides.

The $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\log K_{ML}^M$ or $\log K_{MA}^M$ plots are found to be linear. Comparison of the experimental values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ for catechol with the literature values for some corresponding edta and nta ternary lanthanide complexes reveals the stability sequence $\text{nta} > \text{edta} > \text{cdta}$.

STABILITY constants of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes of the type $[\text{M}(\text{II})\text{-edta-cat}]^1$, where $\text{M}(\text{II}) = \text{Ni}^{2+}$, Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} or Cd^{2+} , $[\text{Ni}(\text{II})\text{-}o\text{-phen-cat}]^2$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{II})\text{-dipy-cat}]^3$ and $[\text{M}(\text{III})\text{-A-cat}]^4$, where $\text{M}(\text{III}) = \text{La}^{3+}$, Pr^{3+} or Nd^{3+} and $A = \text{cdta}$ or nta , have been determined by earlier workers. Stability constants of binary lanthanide-catechol chelates have also been reported recently⁵.

The present work deals with the determination of the stability constants of 1 : 1 binary and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary lanthanide complexes using edta as a primary ligand and catechol (cat), resorcinol (res) or phloroglucinol (phl) as a secondary ligand. Some stability correlations have also been attempted.

Experimental

Standard solutions of catechol, resorcinol and phloroglucinol were prepared in double distilled water by direct weighing. The lanthanide solutions were prepared by dissolving the nitrates of La(III), Ce(III) and Sm(III) in water. Pr(III) and Nd(III) oxides were dissolved in minimum quantity of perchloric acid, excess of which was carefully evaporated and checked before-hand so as to eliminate the possibility of any extra acid in the metal ion solution. EDTA was used as its disodium salt, the two remaining protons were also taken care of.

The usual titration sets i.e. (i) acid, (ii) acid + secondary ligand (L), (iii) acid + L + metal ion (M)

for the binary complexes; and (i) acid + primary ligand (A) + M, (ii) acid + L, (iii) acid + M + A + L for the ternary complexes were prepared. The ionic strength was maintained at $\mu = 0.2M$ (NaClO_4). Dilute solutions ($10^{-3}M$) were used to avoid the possibility of formation of polynuclear species. The sets were titrated pH metrically against 0.2M carbonate free NaOH, at 28° using Irving-Rossotti titration technique⁶.

A digital pH-meter (model Elico-LI-120) was used. Reproducible pH readings were used for calculations. Plots of pH vs alkali added for 1 : 1 binary complexes of La(III) with cat, res and phl and those for the corresponding 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes were worked out.

Results and Discussion

The calculated values of proton-ligand stability constants $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ of the secondary ligands are recorded in Table 1. The metal-ligand stability constants of 1 : 1 binary complexes with

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE SECONDARY LIGANDS
Ionic strength $\mu = 0.2M(\text{NaClO}_4)$; Temp. = 28°

Ligand	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log \beta$
Catechol	9.20	11.70	20.90
Resorcinol	9.07	11.07	20.14
Phloroglucinol	8.90	9.76	18.06

TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1:1 BINARY AND 1:1:1 TERNARY LANTHANIDE COMPLEXES

 Ionic strength $\mu = 0.2M(\text{NaClO}_4)$; Temp. = 28°

Metal ion	$\log K_{MA}^M$	Catechol				Resorcinol				Phloroglucinol			
		$\log K_{ML}^M$	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$-\Delta \log K$	$-\Delta F^*$	$\log K_{ML}^M$	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$-\Delta \log K$	$-\Delta F^*$	$\log K_{ML}^M$	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$-\Delta \log K$	$-\Delta F^*$
La ³⁺	9.31	8.55 (±0.03)	6.20 (±0.03)	2.35	8.59	4.45 (±0.03)	2.10 (±0.04)	2.35	2.91	3.50 (±0.02)	2.20 (±0.03)	1.30	3.05
Ce ³⁺	9.62	8.65 (±0.04)	6.50 (±0.02)	2.15	9.01	4.55 (±0.02)	2.20 (±0.04)	2.35	3.05	3.75 (±0.04)	2.40 (±0.03)	1.35	3.33
Pr ³⁺	9.96	8.90 (±0.04)	6.70 (±0.03)	2.20	9.29	5.05 (±0.04)	2.35 (±0.03)	2.70	3.26	3.90 (±0.03)	2.50 (±0.05)	1.40	3.47
Nd ³⁺	10.56	9.10 (±0.07)	7.00 (±0.05)	2.10	9.70	5.35 (±0.07)	2.50 (±0.05)	2.85	3.47	4.00 (±0.07)	2.60 (±0.02)	1.40	3.60
Sm ³⁺	11.02	9.20 (±0.03)	7.45 (±0.05)	1.75	10.32	5.95 (±0.03)	3.05 (±0.03)	2.90	4.23	4.20 (±0.02)	2.70 (±0.02)	1.50	3.74

 * $-\Delta F = K \text{ cal mole}^{-1}$.

A ($\log K_{MA}^M$) and L ($\log K_{ML}^M$) and of 1:1:1 ternary complexes ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$) along with their standard deviations (in parentheses) are shown in Table 2. The $\Delta \log K$ values i.e. $\log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M$ and the ΔF values for the ternary complexes ($\Delta F = -RT \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$) are also included in this table.

It was observed from the pH plots that the separation of secondary ligand curve from the acid curve took place at $pH \approx 7$ due to ionisation of the phenolic group in the relatively higher pH range. The values of $\bar{n}_H$ obtained in the range $0 < \bar{n}_H < 2$ have been used to calculate $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ for cat, res and phl. The values are in good agreement with those reported in literature^{7,8}. The higher value of $\log K_2^H$ over that of $\log K_1^H$ may be due to lowering of the inductive effect in the second step of ionisation⁹ and also hydrogen bonding¹⁰. The observed sequence of ligand basicity, cat > res > phl, is expected due to a greater proximity of the phenolic groups in catechol.

It was found that the binary complex curve practically overlapped the ligand curve in the lower buffer region, which minimised the possibility of formation of any protonated species¹¹. The separation of the two curves occurred at $pH \approx 5.5$ to 6.0 indicating complexation. The $\bar{n}$ values have been calculated in the pH range where no precipitation was observed. The ternary complex curve separated at lower pH region from the curves of the primary complex and the secondary ligand indicating the formation of the ternary complex. This has been further confirmed by the non-superimposable¹² nature of the theoretical composite curve on the experimental curve of ternary complex. The ternary complex is obviously formed according to the scheme: $M + A \rightleftharpoons MA$; $MA + L \rightleftharpoons MAL$.

A perusal of the values of stability constants (Table 2) shows that the general order is $\log K_{MA}^M \gg \log K_{ML}^M > \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$. The much higher value of $\log K_{MA}^M$ over that of $\log K_{ML}^M$ eliminates

the possibility of ligand displacement, $MA + L \rightleftharpoons ML + A$, in the ternary systems. Any disproportionation of the ternary complex MAL is also discounted as the hexadentate nature of edta will not favour the formation of the species MA_2^{13} . The lower values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ may be due to coulombic repulsion between the negatively charged primary complex MA, $[\text{Ln-edta}]^-$, and the incoming secondary ligand (L^- or L^{2-}). Steric repulsions and statistical considerations are also expected to contribute towards the lowering of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ value as compared to $\log K_{ML}^M$. The $\Delta \log K$ values are consequently negative.

Calculation of % ionisation¹⁴ reveals that the second phenolic-OH in res and phl is very little ionised (res; 0.09-2.4%; phl; 0.2-24%) in the pH range used for calculations. It, therefore, appears reasonable to use only the $\log K_1^H$ value in these two cases for calculating the stability constants. The sequence of stability with respect to the secondary ligands for binary as well as ternary complexes has been found to be cat > res > phl, which is the order of ligand basicities. The variation of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ for the lanthanides shows the expected trend $\text{La}^{3+} < \text{Ce}^{3+} < \text{Pr}^{3+} < \text{Nd}^{3+} < \text{Sm}^{3+}$, which is the order of decreasing ionic radii of the metal ions. The relative complexing tendencies as measured by K_{MA}^M/K_{ML}^M are found to lie in the sequence phl > res > cat; the variations in numerical values being large e.g., 10^6 to 10^2 for the La^{3+} complexes.

Unlike the '3d'-elements, the lanthanides are highly electropositive with large ionic radii and their 4fⁿ electrons are well shielded by the outer lying 5s and 5p orbitals from ligand perturbations. The metal-ligand bond should, therefore, be ionic with a minimal covalent contribution, if at all. Born relation¹⁵ $E = z^2/2r$ (1-1/D) (where E = energy of complexation, z = charge and r = ionic radius of the metal ion) has been tested for the present series of ternary complexes. Plots of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs z^2/r were found to be curved, which may be due to partial covalent nature¹⁶ of the bond and varying degrees of stabilisation caused by the ligand field. Similar

observations¹⁷⁻¹⁹ have been noted for some other lanthanide complexes.

The log K_{MAL}^{MA} values were plotted against log K_{MA}^M and log K_{ML}^M and produced almost linear plots indicating similarity in bonding in the binary and ternary complexes. Slight deviations from linearity may be due to additional steric effects involved in the formation of the ternary complexes.

The variation of log K_{MAL}^{MA} with the standard entropies, S° , of the lanthanides²⁰ showed a linear increase in the stability constant with S° indicating that the changes in free energy during complexation are essentially changes in entropy. A similar trend has been observed for the 1:1 Ln-edta complexes by Foreman and Smith²¹. The stability constants of the ternary complexes increased regularly with increase in the ionic potentials of the lanthanides. This trend is expected in view of the decreasing ionic radii of trivalent lanthanide cations. Standard electrode potentials, E° , of the lanthanides plotted against the stability constants yielded a linear plot. The free energy corresponding to the standard electrode potential comprises mainly the heat of formation of the bare Ln^{3+} ion and its heat of hydration. The latter being the heat of ligation of water molecules, one may expect a gradual increase in log K_{MAL}^{MA} value with decrease in the numerical value of E° (with increasing value of $4f^n$) for the lanthanides.

It is interesting to note an expected trend between our values of log K_{MAL}^{MA} and the reported values for similar ternary systems as shown below :

System	log K_{MAL}^{MA}			Reference
	La^{3+}	Pr^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	
Ln-cdta-cat	4.83	5.69	6.10	4
Ln-edta-cat	6.20	6.70	7.00	Present work
Ln-nta-cat	6.30	6.98	7.36	4

The increase in log K_{MAL}^{MA} values in the order cdta < edta < nta may be due to (i) greater coulombic repulsion in the case of cdta and edta between the primary and secondary ligands than in the case of nta, (ii) availability of more coordination sites for the secondary ligand in the case of nta than for cdta and edta and (iii) between edta and cdta, greater loss of conformational freedom in the case of cdta.

The only comparable values of log K_{MAL}^{MA} for the '3d'-elements as reported by Bhattacharya et al¹ are [Ni(II)-edta-cat], 4.44; [Cu(II)-edta-cat], 7.01 and [Zn(II)-edta-cat], 3.73. The higher value for the Cu(II) complex may be attributed chiefly to Jahn Teller distortion resulting in increased binding energy.

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